

Well-Dawson type polyoxometalates of 3d series and their industrial use as eco-friendly and green catalysts in organic reactions

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Abstract : Based on Well-Dawson heteropoly anion having the formula $[(X^{n+})_2W_{18}O_{62}]^{(16-2n)-}$, two sodium salts $Na_{11}[CuFeW_{18}O_{62}] \cdot 31H_2O$ (1) and $Na_{12}[CuNiW_{18}O_{62}] \cdot 23H_2O$ (2) are synthesized from hydrothermal process and characterized by elemental analysis, thermal analysis, IR analysis, SEM (Scanning Electron Microscope) study and molecular weight determination. The acetylation of *o*-PDA (*o*-phenylenediamine) and their derivatives using these POMs as catalyst form derivatives of benzoxadiazepines.

Keywords : Well-Dawson, heteropolyoxoanion, green catalysts, tungstonickelate.

Introduction

In this paper, we report the synthesis, characterization and catalytic activity of two sodium salts of Well-Dawson HPAs on acetylation of *o*-phenylenediamine (*o*-PDA) and their derivatives 4-methylphenylenediamine and 4-nitrophenylenediamine forming derivatives of benzoxadiazepines which are used as central nervous system stimulants^{1,2}.

Results and discussion

The hydrothermal methods have been applied widely for the synthesis of a large number of POMs in the solid state. We have successfully synthesized two sodium salts of mixed heteropoly tungstates.

In the IR studies of compounds (1) and (2), the peaks at 935 cm^{-1} (w), 939 cm^{-1} (w) can be attributed to $W=O$. The peaks at 844 cm^{-1} (s), 742 cm^{-1} (s) may be due to $W-O-W$ bridge vibration³.

The small but sharp bands at 503 cm^{-1} , 499 cm^{-1} , 432 cm^{-1} depict the presence of $Cu-O$ bond⁴ in Well-Dawson complex (1) and (2). The vibrations in the range of $987-940\text{ cm}^{-1}$ show the presence of $(Ni-O)$ bond⁵ in the Well-Dawson structures of compound (2).

The sharp band at 1099 cm^{-1} and 1016 cm^{-1} are observed for $Fe-O$ ⁶ in compound (1). The broad bands at 3464 cm^{-1} and 3462 cm^{-1} show characteristics peaks for

the stretching of water molecules⁷ in both the compounds

Thermogravimetric (TG) curves for compounds (1) and (2) are shown in Figs. 1 and 2 respectively. The TG curve gives a weight loss of 11% at $150\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for compound (1) and a loss of 8% at $180\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for compound (2)

Fig. 1. $Na_{11}[CuFeW_{18}O_{62}] \cdot 31H_2O$ (1)

Fig. 2. $Na_{12}[CuNiW_{18}O_{62}] \cdot 23H_2O$ (2)

Conclusion :

The performance of Well-Dawson mixed heteropoly oxometalates in the presence of acetyl chloride as acetylating agent for the acetylation of *o*-PDA and their derivatives are studied.

It is observed that a catalytic amount of $\text{Na}_{11}[\text{CuFeW}_{18}\text{O}_{62}]\cdot 31\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1) or $\text{Na}_{12}[\text{CuNiW}_{18}\text{O}_{62}]\cdot 23\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2) is sufficient for the acetylation of amines at 328–333 K. The results also suggest that at the same condition of mole ratio of the reactants, reaction time, temperature and type of amine, nickel containing POMs are more efficient and give better yields. The result also indicates that the nature of the catalysts plays an important role in their catalytic activities. The polyoxometalates of transitional metal have wide industrial application as eco-friendly and green catalysts for the production of effective CNS stimulants.

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